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‘Liberation’ of ‘Younger Brothers’ or Genocide of Subhumans? Genocidal Discourses on Ukrainians in Putin’s Regime

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ABSTRACT

This article explores Russia’s genocidal discourses on Ukrainians, focusing on the predominant narrative that frames cultural genocide as the ‘liberation’ of Ukrainians through the erasure of their cultural identity. Existing literature tends to overlook this form of genocidal discourse, which diverges from typical ‘othering’ by instead claiming that Ukrainians are essentially the same as Russians, with those who wish to maintain their Ukrainian identity seen as needing to be eliminated. In this discourse, the destruction of Ukrainian culture is portrayed as an act of salvation. The more conventional genocidal rhetoric, which calls for the physical extermination of Ukrainians, remains a minority perspective and is primarily propagated by pro-regime ultranationalist hardliners. This article places these discourses within the context of Russia’s long-standing nationalist thought, where the ‘Ukrainian question’ has been a central, existential issue for over a century.

1 | Introduction

Why do Russia’s predominant genocidal discourses on Ukrainians differ from genocidal discourses employed by other political regimes? This article argues that Russia’s predominant genocidal discourses advocate specific forms of cultural genocide, framed as the ‘liberation’ of Ukrainians through the erasure of their cultural identity. What underpins this puzzling logic of the ‘liberation-through-genocide’ discourses on Ukrainians promoted by (pro-)regime actors in Putin’s Russia? The paper also examines the presence of more conventional genocidal discourse akin to that seen in other regimes, such as Nazi Germany or Rwanda during the genocide of the Tutsis, are also present in Russia but they are in minority. Although present within Russia, rhetoric advocating the outright extermination of Ukrainians constitutes a minority strand. Fewer channels promote this discourse compared to the more prevalent narrative of

cultural genocide, as observed within the discursive habitat of (pro-)regime actors. Calls for total extermination have primarily been propagated by ultranationalist hardliners loyal to the regime, including figures affiliated with Yevgeny Prigozhin’s networks prior to his death in a plane explosion in 2023.

The ‘Ukrainian question’ has been a central issue in Russian nationalist thought for centuries. As Pal Kolstø (2023) notes, it is viewed as a more existential concern than any other nationality question in Russia over the past 150 years. For Russia, the end of the war entails Ukraine’s complete subjugation under the ‘Russian world’ and the restoration of its so-called ‘Russian roots’. When Ukrainian resistance proved more resilient than expected, the enemy image shifted. Ukrainians, once perceived as fraternal, were recast as hostile and accused of being deeply penetrated by Nazism, allegedly fostered by the West. In this context, the war’s end is envisioned as the emergence of a ‘new

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Ukrainian identity', rooted in the notion of Ukraine and Russia as a single nation. This perspective frames Russia as a saviour, capable of rescuing Ukraine from the West's 'decadent temptations' (Pynnöniemi and Parppei 2024).

This rationale underpins the predominant 'liberation-through-cultural-genocide' discourse, which is articulated and amplified not only by fringe voices but also by official propagandists and state-affiliated media. Cultural genocide, defined as the systematic destruction of traditions, values, language, and other elements that make one group of people distinct from another, is at the core of these discourses. Novic (2016) highlights cultural genocide as a 'subtle' yet equally destructive process that eliminates a human group through assimilation and dispersion. Its effects are intergenerational, preventing the transmission of cultural identity to future generations, thus perpetuating its impact long after the initial process.

The structure of this article is as follows: First, it introduces general genocidal discourses and explains how Russia's predominant discourse of cultural genocide against Ukrainians is specific and differs from typical dehumanizing genocidal narratives. Next, it details the data collection process and presents empirical findings focusing on the discourse advocating cultural genocide as a solution to the 'Ukrainian question' through the erasure of Ukrainian identity. Finally, the discussion contrasts this predominant narrative with the more traditional, yet minority, genocidal rhetoric advanced by radical ultranationalist elements loyal to Putin's regime.

2 | Genocidal Discourses on Ukrainians in Putin's Regime

Genocidal discourse, as a form of hostile, group-targeted language, represents the most extreme manifestation of negative rhetoric aimed at stigmatizing and dehumanizing a specific group. It refers to a widely used and accepted language of negation, destruction and erasure targeted at a particular group or groups. Genocidal discourse is a more extreme form of negative language than hate speech. It involves the escalation of a widely acceptable language of hatred into language that proposes, promotes or justifies the destruction of a group as acceptable and/or necessary (Townsend 2014).

This language escalates hatred into a tool for proposing or promoting the destruction of a people as necessary or acceptable. The process of enemy construction through 'othering' frames the targeted group as radically different, dehumanizing them to justify violence and war, thereby paving the way for genocidal acts (Irvin-Erickson 2017). Genocidal rhetoric often portrays the out-group as a biological threat, employing metaphors drawn from medical terminology. Perpetrator groups, perceiving themselves as the 'body politic', depict others as viruses, microbes, cancerous growths or parasites that must be eradicated (Savage 2007).

Historical examples include Nazi propaganda, which labelled Jews as 'vermin' or 'diseases' infecting the German nation, using state-controlled media to propagate this discourse (Criado 2022). Similarly, Serb nationalists in the Bosnian

genocide cast Bosniaks as 'Islamic fundamentalists' and existential threats to Serbian identity, linking them to historical Ottoman oppressors (Takševa 2015). In Darfur, the Sudanese government and Janjaweed militias dehumanized non-Arabs by referring to them as 'slaves', 'dogs' or 'donkeys', framing them as racially and culturally inferior to justify systemic attacks (Human Rights Watch 2024; Costello 2009).

During the Rwandan genocide, radio station RTL incited Hutus against Tutsis, calling them *inyenzi* (cockroaches) and *inzoka* (snakes). Such metaphors, reinforced by calls to 'cut down the tall trees', turned neighbours against one another, legitimizing atrocities (Ndahiro 2019). Even beyond nondemocratic regimes, extremist movements have adopted similar genocidal language. For example, Ashin Wirathu, a Buddhist extremist in Myanmar, described Muslims as 'mad dogs' and 'cannibals' while likening them to invasive species like 'African carp' to justify discrimination and violence (Ramakrishna 2020). Neo-Nazi groups and other extremists continue to draw on these dehumanizing tropes to target groups based on racial, religious, or cultural differences.

Similar discursive patterns are evident in Russia, where pro-regime actors openly call for the annihilation of Ukrainians, including women and children, identifying them as enemies of the state. However, existing literature on genocidal dehumanization as a discursive strategy fails to address the distinct nature of predominant Russian genocidal discourses targeting Ukrainians. The extant literature claims that 'the other' is framed and perceived as fundamentally different (Savage 2007, 2009; Ndahiro 2019; Townsend 2014; Irvin-Erickson 2017; Mennecke 2024). However, predominant Russian discourses do not target Ukrainians for being different but rather for refusing to be the same.

In Russia's predominant genocidal discourse, the existential threat to Russia and its national identity is framed as Ukrainians' refusal to conform and 'rejoin the Russian nation'. Unlike typical dehumanizing genocidal narratives, which depict the enemy as radically different, Russia's discourse portrays Ukrainians as part of the same collective who have been led astray by the malign influence of an external 'significant other' and must be corrected or brought back into alignment. This perspective positions Ukrainians as a deviant group, misled by malign external influences, who must be 'cured', 'reprogrammed' or 're-educated' to return to their 'rightful' identity as Russians or inferior 'Little Russians'.

This logic underpins Russia's 'liberation-through-cultural-genocide' discourse, which advocates for the erasure of Ukrainian identity as a form of salvation. Pro-regime actors differ only in the level of brutality they propose, debating how many 'incurable' Ukrainians must be killed, enslaved, deported or sent to concentration camps. This schizophrenic rhetoric frames cultural genocide as a euphemistic 'cure' or 'decolonization', casting the destruction of Ukrainian national identity as an act of liberation.

These discourses appear deeply contradictory, as they advocate for the 'liberation' of Ukrainians by erasing their national identity through what Russia euphemistically calls 'cure' and

‘re-programming’ or by ‘decolonizing’ Ukrainians through colonization. According to this distorted logic, Ukrainians must be ‘saved’ from themselves, which involves their metaphorical or literal destruction in the name of liberation. The rhetoric insists that Ukrainians must spiritually ‘kill the Ukrainian’ within themselves to ‘come to their senses’ and abandon what is framed as their ‘false identity of Ukrainianness’. The ultimate aim of this discourse is to compel Ukrainians to accept their subordinate status as ‘Little Russians’, presented as a form of ‘liberation’ from the ‘virus of fascism’ and the ‘corrupting influence’ of a decadent West.

3 | ‘Othering’ the Same vs. Genocide of Others

While typical genocidal discourses target other groups for not being the same, predominant Russian genocidal discourses want to kill them because they do not want to be the same as perpetrators and accept Russian or inferior ‘Little Russian’ identity. In these predominant discourses, Ukrainians are cast both as perpetrators—implementing ‘fascist’ policies—and as victims of sinister anti-Russian Western plots designed to turn Ukraine into an anti-Russia, posing an existential threat to Putin’s regime and Russia itself. Russian genocidal discourses are rooted in a sense of supremacy that differs from Western racial supremacist ideologies. While Western supremacy has historically been based on the idea of immutable racial hierarchies, Russian supremacism relies on a ‘historical’ notion that peoples can and should alter their identities to fit within the Russian imperial framework. Ukrainians are thus compelled to abandon essential elements of their culture—language, literature, music, and traditions—to shed the stigma of being labelled ‘inferior’, ‘barbaric’ or ‘second-class’ within Russia’s sociopolitical hierarchy (Kotliuk 2023).

Although Russia’s reinvasion of Ukraine in 2022 intensified the division of Ukrainians into ‘right’ and ‘wrong’, this dichotomy has deep historical roots (Riabchuk 2017). During the Soviet era, ‘good’ or ‘right’ Ukrainians—those considered loyal Soviet citizens or ‘Little Russians’—were contrasted with ‘bad’ or ‘wrong’ Ukrainians, labelled as ‘bourgeois nationalists’, ‘Nazi collaborators’ or ‘agents of Western imperialism’. In both historical and contemporary contexts, ‘wrong’ Ukrainians are typically those who maintain a distinct identity separate from Russian influence and support Ukraine’s independence from the USSR or, since 1991, advocate for a Ukraine outside the Russian World. This binary classification mirrors, for example, the historical British perception of the Irish people (Velychenko et al. 2022). This is evident in Russia’s imperial memory policy in the occupied territories. The reinstallation of Lenin statues by Russian occupation authorities symbolizes a neo-Soviet vision of Ukraine, positioned as the ideological antithesis of the post-Maidan Ukraine—one the Kremlin characterizes as an ‘anti-Russian project’ (Zhurzhenko 2023).

Vitaliy Poberezhnyi highlights the concept of Ukrainians’ ‘dual identity’ as central to the imperial memory policy of Putin’s regime. It means that Ukrainians supposedly exist within two cultural spheres: one Ukrainian and the other Russian. According to Putin’s regime, this duality is essential for harmonious coexistence. Recognizing this dynamic helps, for instance, clarify the

Russian rationale behind street renaming initiatives. Almost all Ukrainians whose names were removed from public spaces in Russian-occupied cities held strong anti-Russian sentiments. In contrast, those whose names remain are viewed as embodying this dual identity, even if many never expressed any pro-Russian sentiments. Rather than completely erasing Ukrainian history in occupied territories, Russia seeks to reinterpret it. Ukrainian heroes are expected to occupy a subordinate status compared to their Russian counterparts, much like during the Soviet era (Poberezhnyi 2024).

A core feature of the current (pro-)regime rhetoric is the portrayal of Ukrainians as inherently ‘fascist’, with variations in how deeply this alleged ‘fascism’ is believed to have permeated Ukrainian society. This framing ascribes collective guilt to Ukrainians and debates the severity of the so-called ‘denazification’ process—that is, the erasure of Ukrainian identity—including how many ‘incorrigible’ Ukrainians must be killed. For example, Aleksei Zhuravlev, a State Duma member and leader of the ultranationalist *Rodina* party, stated, ‘Two million [of “incurable” Ukrainians] must be denazified; that is, eliminated’ (Kalikh and Dzhibladze 2023).

The strong Ukrainian resistance to Russian occupation has reinforced the belief among propagandists that the ‘virus of fascism’ is deeply embedded in Ukrainian society, necessitating genocidal actions to address what is perceived as an existential threat to Russian identity and civilization (Medvedev 2020; Stent 2019; Pynnöniemi 2016). As Yevgeniy Nikiforov, director of Orthodox radio Radonezh, declared, ‘The disease is so ingrained that it cannot be cured through persuasion or negotiation. Only surgery is possible there’ (Novye izvestiya 2023).

According to Ukrainian political scientist Mykola Riabchuk, Russians view Ukrainians as a subgroup of their own nation, framing their ‘love’ for Ukrainians as part of an imperial myth. This perspective is unacceptable to Ukrainians, as it denies their distinct national identity. Russian supremacism often incorporates selected Ukrainian cultural symbols to legitimize imperial control, portraying Ukrainians as an exoticized, subordinate ‘Little Russia’. In this narrative, positive traits of Ukrainian culture are attributed to a shared Russian legacy, while negative traits are blamed on external influences, such as Polish, Catholic or Western ‘corruption’ (Riabchuk 2016).

The challenge lies in the fact that this Ukrainian identity is held by the vast majority—tens of millions of people. This paradigm creates an ambiguous liminal space in Russian discourse, which simultaneously proclaims ‘brotherhood’ with ‘Little Russians’ while labeling Ukrainians as ‘extreme nationalists’ and ‘neo-Nazis’ to be eradicated the moment they assert their desire to build an independent nation-state outside the imperialist framework of *Russkiy mir* (Kotliuk 2023). Russia’s discourses toward Ukrainians mix both assimilationist and eliminationist tendencies (Oksamytna 2024).

From the Russian state’s perspective, the Russian and Ukrainian nations should be closely linked under the ‘brotherhood’ narrative or even merged into a single entity through the ‘triume’ concept, which includes Belarus as the third branch of the pan-Russian nation. This denial of a distinct Ukrainian

identity leads to the assertion that the Ukrainian state can only exist with Russia's permission; if Kyiv transforms into an 'anti-Russia', then Ukraine must be 'denationalized' (Laruelle 2023). Violent inclusion of Ukraine also requires the purification of Ukrainians of everything that the Kremlin would consider incompatible with Russia's self-perception as a peculiar and exceptional civilization (Makarychev and Medvedev 2024, 41).

A recurring theme in these discourses is the claim that Ukrainians are fundamentally Russians who have built their identity on rejecting everything Russian. Dmitry Steshin, an ultranationalist war correspondent for *Komsomolskaya Pravda*, echoed this view:

[It is] a horrid deviation, because at its root is their denial of themselves. Therefore, you can't consider them as people with full-fledged morality and normal mental apparatus [...] They would like to get rid of *rusnya* [Russian invaders]. This is incredible, since they are Russian themselves! How do you erase that part of your brain that controls your ethnic, cultural identity? But any person who takes on the identity as a citizen of independent Ukraine ... rejects himself, rejects the entire Russian culture. And if you, being Russian by culture, reject the Russian culture, what is left within you, what do you become? You simply become an animal!

(Julia Davis 20.11.2022a, 2022b, 2022c)

Petr Akopov, a propagandist for RIA Novosti, stated: 'What is Ukraine? It is historical Russia. Its population is the same Russians, not only those who consider themselves Russians but also those called Ukrainians, i.e., Little Russians, one of the three constituent parts of the Russian people' (Akopov 2023). Similarly, Andrei Medvedev, deputy director of VGTRK (*Vserossiyskaya gosudarstvennaya televizionnaya i radioveshchatelnaya kompaniya*, or All-Russian State Television and Radio Broadcasting Company) remarked, 'Russians killed Russians just because some of them started to consider themselves Ukrainians' (VGTRK 2015). This discourse tolerates Ukrainian cultural expression only as ethnographic folklore, rejecting any notion of Ukrainians as a sovereign modern nation.

Within this discourse, Ukrainians are portrayed as inherently inferior and dependent on Russia for their identity and success (Davis 2024). Russian propagandists, such as Ivan Lizan, have described Ukrainians as incapable of creating 'anything sophisticated, including the state as a complex social organism' (Lizan 2023). Ukrainians are depicted as victims of Western influence, unable to see the harm of rejecting Russia, and Ukraine is portrayed as a failed state incapable of providing for its population (Pynnöniemi 2016, 93). This leads to the justification that the only solution for Ukrainians is reintegration into Russia, where they can 'become somebody' within the empire.

In historical and contemporary Russian literature, media, and societal discourses, Ukrainian people and their leaders have consistently been portrayed as backwards, unsophisticated, indolent, unreliable, cunning, prone to thievery and selfish—and

thus in need of imperial guidance. In both folk Russian discourse and contemporary entertainment media, Ukrainians are often depicted as lazy, stupid and useless, whereas Russia is portrayed as a wealthy, advanced and benevolent state that generously supported its former territories. Within this narrative, Russians are cast as the wise 'older brothers', while Ukrainians and other neighbouring peoples assume the roles of dim-witted, backward relatives—figures typically mocked for their perceived incompetence (Oksamytna 2023; Riabchuk 2016, 78).

Such ridicule reflects a deeply embedded sense of Russian superiority over its colonial subjects, who are commonly portrayed as lazy, immature and unreliable. Humour and jokes targeting Ukrainians and their political leaders function to reinforce these entrenched stereotypes, sustain Russia's self-perception of regional dominance and normalize hierarchies of power. By framing imperialist attitudes as benevolence, this form of humour obscures underlying structures of domination while promoting the narrative of Russia as a magnanimous and civilizing force (Minchenia et al. 2018, 225–228).

The Kremlin's concept of 'historical Russia' frames Ukraine, Belarus and Russia as parts of a singular, united entity defined by shared language, faith and values. This discourse asserts that the 'divided Russian nation' has a sovereign right to reunification, legitimizing the Kremlin's actions to prevent Ukraine from detaching from 'historical Russia' under Western influence. By doing so, Russia claims to be mending the 'artificial divide' between the peoples (Komin 2024).

This perspective further assumes that Ukraine's existence is tied to Russia's civilizational sphere and that it has no political or historical legitimacy outside of this framework. Following Ukraine's surrender, the Kremlin envisions extensive ideological, cultural and educational efforts to eradicate Ukrainian national identity and transform it into a compliant part of the 'Russian world'. Russian debates openly admit this vision involves systematic oppression and dismantling of Ukraine's existing political and social systems. The war is framed as a necessary response to Ukraine's evolution into an 'anti-Russia', a development that Russian propagandists argue threatens the very fabric of 'historical Russia' (Pynnöniemi and Parppe 2024; Davis 2024).

4 | Data Collection

I collected data on genocidal discourses targeting Ukrainians in Russia from both official and unofficial sources, analysing a wide range of actors, including state officials, propagandists and pro-war nationalist influencers, primarily on Telegram. While I intentionally sought out examples of genocidal discourse, my selection is illustrative rather than exhaustive, reflecting prominent voices in Russia's public sphere.

Discourses on Ukrainians in Putin's Russia are co-shaped by official state actors, state-controlled media and pro-war hardliners who amplify these narratives on social media. These discourses are tacitly supported by the regime, as anti-war narratives in Russia are criminalized (Radio Svoboda 2024b). This is arguably the only form of pluralism permitted in contemporary

TABLE 1 | Selected ultranationalist channels and number of subscribers.

Telegram channel	10 Apr. 2021 ^a	10 Jan. 2022	10 Jan. 2023	10 Jan. 2024	10 Jan. 2025
Vladlen Tatarskiy (Maxim Fomin)	13,239	23,684	523,165	328,142	236,524
Govorit TopaZ	5179	5826	49,055	114,215	151,045
DShRG Rusich ^b	—	—	49,743	141,599	248,786
Zapiski avantyurista (Igor ‘Bereg’ Mangushev)	4024	5651	50,943	34,212	27,609
Strelkov Igor Ivanovich	11,893	15,112	791,835	557,419	411,592
Vladislav Ugolnyi	—	512	39,022	47,200	44,984
Ryadovoi Gubarev (Pavel Gubarev)	809	696	54,554	37,642	30,971
Syny monarkhii	8229	13,278	34,196	51,132	73,331
Obyknovennyi tsarizm ^c	—	—	23,244	34,406	39,584
Trinadtsatyi (Egor Guzenko) ^d	—	—	81,150	217,085	280,634

Source: <https://tgstat.ru/>.

^aOlder data is not available. These five dates, spanning five consecutive years, were selected to capture the relevance and evolving dynamics of popularity within these Telegram channels—from the preinvasion period, when Telegram and these specific channels had yet to gain widespread traction, even though some had existed well before the reinvasion.

^bFounded in September 2022.

^cFounded in February 2022.

^dFounded in March 2022.

Russia regarding Ukrainians and Russia’s war in Ukraine. In this context, it can be challenging to distinguish between official and unofficial sources, as some individuals work for state propaganda while also managing private Telegram channels, making it unclear whether their statements reflect personal views on Ukraine and Ukrainians or represent the official stance of state-controlled media.

These actors (officials, propagandists and nonstate pro-war hardliners) create a discursive habitat—the combined work of the state administration and a whole constellation of ideological entrepreneurs, both individual and institutional. It is not a uniform cohesive group, and it draws on an eclectic doctrinal stock and multiple repertoires and intellectual genealogies. This realm operates in a competitive market for ideas, with a whole ecosystem of ideological entrepreneurs, producers and subcontractors (Laruelle 2023). The genocidal discourses in Russia, coming from such discursive habitat, range from advocacy of cultural genocide to explicit calls for physical genocide, particularly on Telegram channels run by hardliners. Advocates of physical genocide often use Nazi-like rhetoric, portraying Ukrainians as subhuman and unfit for the Russian Empire, arguing that their extermination is necessary for the glory of Russia.

My research examined over 50 Russian state officials, propagandists and pro-regime nonstate actors who were particularly vocal in promoting genocidal discourses—specifically, those who frequently addressed the so-called ‘Ukrainian question’ more frequently than others on pro-regime Telegram channels, which tend to concentrate on different themes—such as battlefield developments, as is typical of many so-called *Z-voyenkory* (pro-war correspondents and bloggers). Propagandists encompass media managers, journalists, talk show hosts and individuals shaping the ideological course, including political and public

figures, theorists and ideologists (Kalikh and Dzhibladze 2023). On Telegram, I analysed the content of ten prominent channels disseminating genocidal rhetoric from February 2022 to September 2024. With over 40 million users, Telegram has surpassed WhatsApp as Russia’s most popular messaging service (Garner 2023).

State-controlled official media and Telegram channels serve as the primary sources of data for this paper. Official media play a crucial role in Putin’s regime and are inseparable from the state’s operations. These outlets function as part of the regime’s machinery, legitimizing its actions. For example, Russian state media managers were even awarded military medals for their contributions during the annexation of Crimea in 2014 (Pomerantsev 2022). Additional data sources include weekly digests of Russian propaganda, such as Julia Davis’s updates on Twitter (now X) and the Russian Media Monitor on YouTube.

On Telegram, I observed networks of pro-war hardliners, including channels operated by groups and individuals associated with the former Wagner Group and Evgeniy Prigozhin (see Table 1). The Wagner Group had connections to other structures and influencers, such as the military unit Rusich (‘DShRG Rusich’) and individuals like Egor Guzenko (‘Trinadtsatyi’) and Evgeniy Rasskazov (‘Topaz’), a neo-Nazi militant from Donbas turned blogger, who recently joined the 88th Battalion ‘Española’, a unit composed of neo-Nazi Russian football hooligans (Ruskiy Styag 2022; Mirskiy 2022; Shalunov 2022; Radio Svoboda 2024a). Before the 2022 reinvasion, he worked as a correspondent for Czar.tv, an ultranationalist monarchist pro-Kremlin podcast and streaming service (Alperovich 2022).

Bloggers linked to ex-Wagner Group play a significant role in shaping public opinion in Russia. These actors operate several Telegram channels, some with tens or hundreds of thousands of

followers (Dalton 2023). One prominent ultra-nationalist blogger and influencer affiliated with the Wagner Group was Igor Mangushev ('Bereg'), who ran the Telegram channel *Notes of an Adventurer* ('Zapiski avanturista'). Mangushev founded the Orthodox-nationalist movement Bright Russia ('Svetlaya Rus') in 2008–2009, which was previously involved in targeting locations frequented by illegal immigrants (Tumanov 2015). Before the 2022 reinvasion, Mangushev worked as a senior manager at the Internet Research Agency, Prigozhin's troll factory in St. Petersburg (Kovalev 2022). Later, he operated in Africa (reportedly in the Central African Republic) and in Russia, organizing disinformation campaigns and provocations against democratic opposition.

I also analysed channels, posts, and announcements from ultra-nationalists linked to the now-defunct Angry Patriots Club ('Klub rasserzhennykh patriotov'), such as *Soldatskaya Pravda* (led by Mikhail 'Khrustalik' Polynkov) and *Ryadovoi Gubarev*. Pavel Gubarev, a militant pro-Russian leader in Donetsk during spring 2014, later distanced himself from Igor Girkin. Initially allies, with Gubarev praising Girkin on air and discussing shared political projects, their relationship deteriorated after Girkin's imprisonment in 2023. Since then, Gubarev has repeatedly insulted Girkin, accusing him of being a liar, schemer, hysterical and narcissist who fails to keep promises (Voroshilov 2023).

I also included Orthodox ultra-nationalists associated with the neo-fascist *Tsargrad* channel, owned by Konstantin Malofeyev, and their ties to other similarly oriented networks. For instance, the Telegram channel *Ordinary Tsarism* ('Obyknovennyi tsarizm'), co-founded by ultranationalist publicists Yegor Kholmogorov, Artemiy Sych and Svyat Pavlov, is also linked to regime propaganda outlets—Kholmogorov and Pavlov work for *Rossiya Segodnya*. Another example is the *Sons of Monarchy* ('Syny monarkhii') Telegram channel, administered by Roman Antonovskiy, who is also employed by Russia Today (Britskaya and Prokushev 2023).

Within Russia's state propaganda apparatus, the Kremlin does not directly dictate content or set headlines. Instead, it relies on state propagandists to take the initiative, expecting them to interpret and align with the regime's goals. Producers and presenters at state-controlled media outlets may have varying ideas about how best to frame narratives, tailoring their work to what they believe will align with the preferences of their superiors. These differing approaches often manifest in various programs, with individuals hoping their efforts gain recognition and approval. This system effectively harnesses effort, imagination, enthusiasm and ambition without the need for top-down micro-management (Galleotti 2019).

The discursive habitat concerning Ukrainians in Russia appears to operate in a similar way—not through direct orders from the Kremlin, but with a degree of autonomy that allows actors to craft their own discourses. These propagandists and pro-regime figures intuitively understand the regime's boundaries and informal constraints, knowing what they can say and what would cross the line. Official propaganda, along with the regime and its affiliated actors, aligns itself with the broader aspirations, grievances and ideological frameworks of the Russian establishment.

These actors articulate desires, ambitions and complexes that the establishment itself prefers not to express directly, providing a 'service' that includes disseminating genocidal discourses. By not criminalizing such narratives, the regime overtly or tacitly endorses them.

Genocidal discourses are systematically propagated through state media and social media. It is well-established that state-controlled media do not disseminate any information or opinions without the explicit approval of the Presidential Administration (Ioffe 2023). In this paper, I selected specific messages, posts and statements from within this discursive habitat, focusing on pro-regime media and Telegram channels. The selection was based on keywords associated with Ukrainians, such as *cure*, *reprogramming*, *re-education*, *extermination* and *annihilation*. These terms were chosen as they provide clear evidence of genocidal discourses. As a next step, posts and statements containing explicit genocidal rhetoric were classified into two main categories of genocidal discourse: those promoting cultural genocide of Ukrainians and those advocating total genocide, as seen in cases such as Nazi Germany and Rwanda.

5 | Cultural Genocide as Liberation

The genocidal discourse on Ukrainians, unlike typical dehumanizing war propaganda aimed at 'othering' the enemy, focuses on 'cure', 're-programming' and 're-education' to make Russians, or at least 'Little Russians' out of Ukrainians back again to 'de-other' them. The only thing in which these actors differ is how brutal this process must be and how many Ukrainians should be killed, deported or sent to concentration camps. The puzzle is that Ukrainian nation is depicted as needing salvation through purifying violence and cultural genocide, to be reinvented as 'Little Russians' subordinate to empire as a 'brotherly nation' (Kolstø 2023; Nicolosi 2022). Russian propagandist Viktoria Nikiforova, working from 2020 in RIA Novosti, stated:

It is necessary to save Ukrainians from themselves, not have baby talks with patients and not look at the 'international community', which still dreams of destroying us anyway. We bring them [Ukrainians] the truth. The truth is that we are one people and must live in peace

(Nikiforova 2022).

Violence is intended to 'liberate' Ukrainians from their 'falsely acquired' identity and bring them back to their original roots as 'younger brothers', 'Little Russians'. This paternalism resembles the past atrocious colonial crimes in the name of 'salvation' of 'the natives' (Dudko 2022, 137; Oksamytna 2023, 503). The 'liberation-through-cultural genocide' discourse aims to force Ukrainians to renounce their national and political identity. In this discourse, 'denazification', a code word for violent 'de-Ukrainization', is the main tool of the 'liberation'. According to Russian propaganda logic, 'Ukrainian' is synonymous with 'Nazi', and Nazism is an inherent part of Ukrainian national identity. Thus, the idea of full-scale 'de-Nazification' in

(pro)regime discourse is explicitly genocidal, targeting most Ukrainians (Dudko 2022).

Russian (pro)regime discourse calls for ‘reeducating’ Ukrainians through violence in a colonial war of conquest. It believes that Ukrainians need to be forcefully shown that their true fulfilment lies within the empire, as they are deemed incapable of handling independence and sovereignty due to their supposed inferiority. This mindset leads to viewing Western influence as insidious, with Ukrainians being used as pawns against Russia. By forcibly removing this influence, Russia believes it is liberating Ukraine from Western colonization and preserving its own values. Those who resist this ‘reeducation’ are seen as stubbornly clinging to their Ukrainian identity and considered worthy of physical elimination.

Also, Ukrainians should be ‘cured’, which involves violence, complete subordination, and cultural extermination of the entire sovereign nation. The most sinister part is the implication that Ukrainians should be grateful for their own cultural genocide. The genocidal notion of ‘cure’ suggests that Ukrainians are ‘sick’ and must be rid of this disease, implying that Russians are doing them a favour by violently pushing them back into their perceived inferior identity, having been ‘deluded’ by the corrupt influence of the West and their domestic ‘puppets’—Nazis, fascists and Banderites. Second, Ukrainian children should be ‘re-educated’, which also implicitly means that Russian occupation forces do a favour to them.

6 | ‘Cure’ of Ukrainians From Ukrainian Identity as a Way to Liberation

In current Russia’s pro-war discourses, liberation is the ultimate goal, while the ‘cure’—cultural genocide—is the means: ‘Liberating minds that have been repeatedly poisoned by the Russophobic authorities’, as Oleg Karpovich, Director of the Institute of Contemporary Studies at the Diplomatic Academy of the Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, stated (Karpovich 2022). The ‘cure’ is presented as a benevolent act—people should want to be cured from the disease and recuperate. Implicitly, this means that Russian occupants are doing a favour to those who are stupid or brainwashed enough to understand the goodness of such intentions.

Part of the ‘cure’ involves ‘killing Ukrainians in themselves’ in a spiritual sense, transforming them into individuals willing to abandon their identity and subordinate to Russia. Ukrainians essentially face two choices: accept Russian identity (to be ‘cured’) or be killed (Syny monarchii 8.9.2022; Obyknovennyi tsarizm 4.4.2023). The crucial goal of the Russian state in the occupied territories, referred to as ‘new territories’ or ‘post-Ukrainian territories’ in Russia, is to ‘change the [...] consciousness of today’s Ukrainians’ as former president Dmitriy Medvedev posted (Dmitriy Medvedev 5.4.2022).

Russian ultranationalist publicist Yegor Kholmogorov declared, ‘Every Ukrainian must be killed. There shouldn’t be any Ukrainians. I’m sure most unhappy Russians will find the

strength to kill the Ukrainian in themselves. We will help the rest of them’ (Kholmogorov 22.8.2022). Similarly, Aleksandr Matyushin, a fascist from Donetsk Oblast and former participant in pre-2014 marginal pro-Russian secessionist movements, advocated for complete Russification. He called for Ukrainians to ‘kill the Ukrainian in themselves’, arguing that they had once ‘killed the Russian in themselves’. (Ukraina.ru 2022).

The Russian occupation is frequently presented as a form of spiritual liberation. Crimean secessionist leader Sergei Aksyonov claimed that the Russian army ‘liberates the Ukrainian land from evil spirits ... After liberation, Ukraine will need ... also serious spiritual treatment’ (Aksyonov Z 82 30.3.2022). Propagandist Anton Krasovskiy, director of Russian-language broadcasting on the state-controlled broadcaster RT from 2020, stated, ‘our task is to cleanse the soul of our people from evil. Of course, the people who live in the territories that used to be called Ukraine are our people. And our task is to cleanse their souls. That’s what the [war] is being done for’ (Krasovskiy 2022). Saving the immortal soul and cleansing it from ‘neo-Nazism’ is the main goal of so-called ‘de-nazification’, according to pro-regime publicist Vladimir Skachko, with the aim of ‘conscious acquirement of a new identity’ (Skachko 2023).

The rationale for such spiritual treatment is that, as one of the most notorious Russian propagandists, Vladimir Solovyov, noted: ‘hated [for Russia] was nurtured in Ukrainians for years ... Our poor brotherly nation has gone astray. We will cure them, we will help, we will rebuild’ (Russian Media Monitor 2023a). Pseudo-historian Mikhail Smolin calls for removing Ukrainian ‘false identity’ as a ‘harmful virus’. He considers Ukrainians to be brainwashed people who must be liberated through psychotherapy. He asserts no one is born Ukrainian; a person ‘becomes Ukrainian as a result of a long processing’ (*obrabotka*) (Kolstø 2023).

There is a consensus within the discursive habitat that this ‘cure’ must involve brutality and violence. Filmmaker Karen Shakhnazarov suggested methods such as ‘concentration camps, re-education, and sterilization’ (Anderson 2022). At times, this brutal ‘cure’ discourse escalates to calls for apocalyptic, purifying violence. Ukrainians are depicted as ‘possessed’ by the devil, requiring a cure through the destruction of their cities and the mass killing of millions. Pavel Gubarev, one of the leaders of the (pro)Russian secessionists in Donbas in 2014, stated in October 2022:

They [Ukrainians] are Russian people, possessed by the demon. We are not going to kill them; we want to change their minds. But if you don’t want us to change your minds, we will kill you. We will kill as many of you as we have to. We will kill one million, five million. We can exterminate all of you, until you realize that you are possessed and you have to be cured.

(Severodonetsk.novyny 2022)

In another public appearance, Gubarev said: ‘We will have to re-educate them [Ukrainians]: send some to concentration camps,

reassure some with actions, not just words. The truth is ours, so it will have to be done anyway. To do that, we have to win first. Win at all costs and kill as many people as it is needed' (LobanIzdat 2023). The 'cure' should be implicitly easy because Ukrainian identity is seen by these pro (regime) actors not as a nationality, but 'a political ideology, the purpose of which is to kill Russians and fight Russia' (Syny monarkhii 8 September 2022). These actors in the discursive habitat understand forcing Ukrainians to adopt (Little) Russian identity as a return to 'normality'. Vladlen Tatarskiy, pro-Kremlin blogger from Donbas killed in April 2023, said that:

A Ukrainian is a Russian who got sick. Like a transvestite, he was born a man, then [...] decided to become a woman and live like one. [...] A Ukrainian is a Russian spiritual transvestite, who is trying to squeeze into another skin. I was always interested: when was this moment when they have shifted from a healthy Russian person [...] into total schizophrenia? The future of Ukraine, those people who live there, is that they are Russian people and they will return to their normal state.

(Julia Davis 2022a, 2022b, 2022c)

Russian singer Yulia Chicherina, who frequently performs for Russian soldiers in occupied Ukraine, expressed similar sentiments on her Telegram channel. On 31 December 2022, she wrote: 'It's time to settle the score. My advice to the Ukies [Ukrainians]—surrender. All your sins will freeze in our Gulags, and you will return cleansed to our Russian world, which will melt everything' (Yulia Chicherina, 31 December 2022). In another post, she stated: 'I advise you to surrender. Don't be afraid of our "gulags". They'll give you noodles, and most of you won't face a life sentence—you still have to earn that. Quickly cleanse yourselves and rejoin our Russian world. You'll live, and we will teach your children and grandchildren loyalty and love for the Motherland. Welcome back to the Russian world!' (Yulia Chicherina, 1 November 2023).

Igor Mangushev ('Bereg'), ultranationalist mercenary and former senior manager at the Prigozhin's troll factory gave a macabre performance in a Moscow club brandishing a Ukrainian soldier's skull on stage in front of a crowd he claimed to kill during the siege of Mariupol at Azovstal. During his performance in August 2022, he said: 'We are at war against an idea – the idea of Ukraine as an anti-Russian state. There can be no peace. Ukraine must be de-Ukrainized. Little Russian lands must be retrieved. Everyone who considers themselves to be Ukrainian will be eliminated. That's why we don't care how many of them [Ukrainians] we have to kill ... they all need to be destroyed' (Korshak 2023). In the end, he was killed by his own, probably Chechens, in occupied Kadiivka in February 2023. Journalist Mikhail Khazin proposed: 'Ukraine to dismember and millions of unwanted Ukrainians to exterminate' (Andriy 2017).

7 | 'Re-Education' ('Perevospitanie') of Ukrainian Children

A significant part of the (pro)regime's discourse on 'liberation-through-genocide' focuses on Ukrainian children that should

be 're-educated'—indoctrinated and militarized—in order to grow up as loyal Russians, willing to sacrifice themselves for Putin and the Russian empire. 'To raise their [Ukrainian] children as Russian' is the mantra repeated in Russia's discursive habitat (Zapiski avantyurista, 2 April 2022a, 25 August 2022b). It is closely linked to the 'cure' of Ukrainians through 'liberation'. As Russian propagandist Anna Dolgareva explicitly stated—'Ukrainians should be destroyed and their children raised in the Russian spirit' (NeShutki, 15.2.2023).

Andrey Kartapolov, a member of Russia's State Duma, proposed relocating Ukrainian children from occupied territories to military boarding schools in Russia to ensure their 're-education' from what he termed 'Ukrainian Nazism'. Anton Krasovskiy, the head of Russian-language broadcasting for the state-owned RT channel, declared that Ukrainian children who refuse to accept Russian identity should be drown and burnt alive (Ioffe 2023). Some actors in the regime's discursive habitat believe that Ukrainians are a lost cause for their imperial project, unlike their children. Yuri Kot, a pro-government pundit, asserted, 'They're enemies, just enemies ... The enemy's children can be re-educated, but the enemy himself must be eliminated!' (Francis Scarr 11 January 2023). Russian senator Konstantin Dolgov compared Ukrainian children to the Hitlerjugend, saying:

Everything that was jammed into their [Hitlerjugend] heads had to be beaten out. We will certainly do the same to these [Ukrainian] children! ... This is not an easy job. Many were infected by these bacteria! [...] Unfortunately, these generations are already ruined, those that are growing up. But I'm certain that many of them can be saved. I don't mean just physically [...] but to save them intellectually and psychologically! Even mentally, we'll be doing this for a long time ...

(Russian Media Monitor 2023b)

Maria Lvova-Belova, the Children's Ombudsman, said at the St. Petersburg International Legal Forum that special programs are needed to re-educate children, overcoming the propaganda conducted in Ukraine (Kol'tsova 2023).

8 | Discussion: Total Genocide vs. Cultural Genocide

Meanwhile, some hardline factions within Russia's discursive environment align more closely with traditional genocidal rhetoric, rejecting the possibility that Ukrainians could be 'cured' or even needing to be cured at all. These hardliners emphasize a complete dismissal of any shared identity or sense of fraternity, instead portraying Ukrainians as a separate, inherently 'anti-Russian' group deserving of annihilation. This narrative is akin to genocidal discourses in Nazi Germany, targeting Jews or in Rwanda, targeting Tutsis, where racialized and dehumanizing ideologies justified their extermination.

In these discourses, Ukrainians are depicted as subhuman 'wreckers', their mere existence seen as a threat to the imperial

vision of a 'Greater Russia'. This ideology not only justifies but also glorifies extreme violence. Affiliates of the former Wagner Group embody this mindset, serving as symbols of its brutal and sadistic nature. Moreover, these discourses have been partly absorbed into the state's official narrative, marking a period of unchecked violence that highlights the transformation of Putin's regime into one that celebrates cruelty, fostering an environment where genocidal acts are not merely tolerated but actively promoted (Medvedev 2023).

This perspective, though currently held by a minority, emerges from certain state propagandists—such as Georgiy Mamsurov from the army's TV channel (TV Zvezda) and Dmitriy Steshin—as well as from ultranationalists and neo-Nazis associated with groups like the Rusich and former Prigozhin's network. Key figures, including Evgeniy Rasskazov, Vladislav Ugolnyi and Igor Mangushev, have amplified these views on Telegram channels, which serve as an unregulated, uncensored battleground for propagating extreme war narratives. Telegram has become a platform where graphic depictions of human suffering, injury and death are shared at unprecedented scale and speed, pushing the boundaries of what is considered acceptable content (Hoskins and Shchelin 2023).

At the heart of the genocidal rhetoric advocating for the total extermination of Ukrainians is the belief that they are incapable of being re-educated or 'cured'. This belief leads to the conclusion that the only solution is to eliminate them entirely. Georgiy Mamsurov from TV Zvezda expressed this sentiment, saying, 'I see no options to re-educate them. This is impossible. What I saw with my own eyes, the way these people acted, is nonsense. They are "animals"' (STV 2022). Similarly, Dmitriy Steshin, in a now-deleted YouTube video, stated, 'I do not believe in any re-education. Recent history has shown that people who accept this [Ukrainian] identity cannot be re-educated because it is based on hatred of Russians. It is impossible to re-educate a person *who hates us for unknown reasons* [italics added by the author], who, in fact, hates himself. He must be cured with electricity or liquidated' (YouTube undated).

Pro-war blogger Yegor Guzenko ('Trinadtsatyi') shared his view that 'Ukropism [a derogatory term for Ukrainian national identity] is a virus that affects the central nervous system and can only be treated with lead. Or forced labor, as a last resort' (Trinadtsatyi, 23 December 2023). He further claimed, 'The enemy has neither sex nor age. Tomorrow, these children will grow up to be new Banderites, and there will be no cure for them. This virus can only be cured by destroying the infected. They are no longer human' (Trinadtsatyi, 2 April 2024; Dryachuk 2024). These dehumanizing genocidal narratives are often linked with intense anti-Semitism, as seen in attacks on President Zelenskyi as a 'clown Kike' or claims that Ukraine is under Jewish control. This reflects a peculiar strain of pro-regime neo-Nazism in Russia, where many followers openly identify as Nazis or express admiration for Hitler, creating rhetoric that can be both contradictory and surreal (Garner 2023, 125–126).

A striking example of this genocidal discourse can be found in the Telegram channel of Rusich. The Rusich group uses social media as a propaganda tool, presenting its members as fearsome

warriors despite their relatively small numbers during their involvement in Ukraine (Rondeaux et al. 2022). After their withdrawal from Donbas in 2015, Rusich fought in Syria and possibly in Africa (Libya, CAR) as part of the Wagner Group (@leonidragozin, 2022). This propaganda serves to bolster their image as ultra-nationalists engaged in a righteous struggle, while simultaneously spreading their extreme ideology and supporting the regime's genocidal narrative. Rusich was redeployed to Ukraine following Russia's invasion in February 2022.

The Rusich's Telegram channel consistently propagates genocidal rhetoric, repeatedly calling for the total annihilation of perceived enemies. One post advocated for the killing of all Ukrainians—regardless of age or gender—arguing that children would grow up to avenge their parents (DShRG Rusich, 5 August 2023b). Another stated, 'We need to kill as many Ukrainians as possible, regardless of gender or age, in order to live peacefully at home and in the liberated territories' (DShRG Rusich, 2 April 2023a). A third post declared: 'They are not people but sick animals who will never become Russian. War does not tolerate compassion—there are no civilians or children. When they are all buried alive in their homes, we will win' (DShRG Rusich, 8 August 2024).

This brutal ideology is echoed by former Rusich member Evgeniy Rasskazov ('Topaz'). Rasskazov publishes posts reflecting his view of the future of Ukrainians. In one, for example, he says that the wives of dead Ukrainian soldiers should be 'employed as prostitutes in saunas near Moscow so that the girls can earn money to feed their children', and he calls Ukrainians 'pathetic creatures, practically cockroaches' who will soon be forced 'to work for Russia in harmful industries' (Alperovich 2022). Rasskazov also stated that he derives sexual pleasure from killing Ukrainian soldiers and making their families cry (Sergej Sumlenny 28 August 2022; Dalton 2023). Later, Rasskazov joined the Española Battalion, a Russian irregular military unit formed from football hooligans and led by Stanislav Orlov, known by his call sign 'Ispanets' (Spaniard), the former leader of the Red-Blue Warriors hooligan gang in Moscow (Fokht et al. 2023; Akhmedova 2023).

Another neo-Nazi blogger, Vladislav Ugolnyi (real name Sergienko), who works as an RT correspondent and influencer, hails from Donetsk and has been a propagandist for the self-declared Donetsk People's Republic. He refers to Ukrainians as 'subhumans' and advocates for their complete biological annihilation. He explicitly stated: '*Khokhols* [a derogatory term for Ukrainians] are degenerates and they should all be killed. Every *khokhol*, *khokhlushka*, and *khokhlenok* [derogatory terms for Ukrainians]. When the *khokhol* was born, the Jew cried. But we will kill them all sooner or later' (Vladislav Ugolnyi, 18 July 2023a). In other posts, he added: 'I despise them [Ukrainians]. This filth and gangrene on the body of my people deserves nothing but death' (Vladislav Ugolnyi, 30 November 2023b), and 'Any person who associates themselves with the Ukrainian state project independent from Moscow is a subhuman' (Vladislav Ugolnyi, 4 August 2022).

While the call for total genocide is supported by a relatively small number of individuals and promoted through the *Rusich's* Telegram channel, the idea of cultural genocide—using the

argument that Ukrainians must be killed to force them to become Russians—dominates Russia's broader genocidal discourses. This rhetoric is pervasive in everyday Russian propaganda, amplified by both official and unofficial channels. Cultural genocide is particularly prevalent and closely linked to the highest levels of power in Putin's Russia. Some scholars argue that Putin himself believes that those resisting in Ukraine are not true Russians and, therefore, must be eradicated (Plokhly and Higgins 2023).

9 | Conclusion

The empirical findings in this paper confirm that, unlike traditional genocidal rhetoric that centres on eliminating distinct and irreconcilable 'others', Russia's dominant discourses are uniquely focused on 'de-othering'—forcible assimilation of Ukrainians by erasing their national identity and their redefinition as part of the pan-Russian nation. This distorted logic of 'liberation-through-cultural-genocide' frames the destruction of Ukrainian culture as an act of salvation, wherein Ukrainians are supposedly 'freed' from their perceived false identity. These narratives have been weaponized to justify the atrocities committed during Russia's war against Ukraine, reinforcing a culture of supremacy within Russia's political and ideological systems.

At the core of Russia's genocidal discourse is a historical narrative that denies the legitimacy of Ukrainian nationhood. This rhetoric is further amplified by claims that Ukraine is an 'artificial state' created by malign Western influence and sustained by 'Nazism', which Putin's regime equates with Ukrainian nationalism. Such narratives position Ukrainians not as entirely foreign, but as errant members of the Russian family who must be 'reclaimed' through violent means. This ideological framing creates a dichotomy: Ukrainians are both victims of Western manipulation and perpetrators of an existential threat to Russian civilization. The result is a schizophrenic discourse that dehumanizes and infantilizes Ukrainians, reducing their identity to a malleable construct that Russia must forcibly reshape.

The central aim of these genocidal discourses is to create a generation of Ukrainians who identify as Russians, thus ensuring the erasure of Ukrainian culture and national memory. The regime's propagandists often reframe this process with euphemisms such as 're-education', 'denazification' or 'decolonization', presenting cultural eradication as a moral necessity to rescue Ukraine from Western ideological corruption.

Among the limited pluralism within pro-regime actors, the discourse of cultural genocide is dominant but not exclusive. A more extreme and less widespread strand within the regime's ideological framework calls for the physical extermination of Ukrainians who resist assimilation. Radical figures in Russia's propaganda ecosystem, including ultranationalist bloggers and Telegram channels linked to groups like Rusich, openly advocate for the wholesale slaughter of Ukrainians, portraying them as subhuman or as a 'biological threat' to Russia.

The dominant discourses of cultural genocide in Russia are not confined to fringe elements; they are deeply entrenched in the regime's official propaganda apparatus and supported by

influential state figures. This discursive ecosystem operates with tacit approval from the Kremlin, which allows such rhetoric to thrive while criminalizing anti-war dissent. The result is a competitive landscape of ideologues and propagandists vying to outdo each other in their expressions of loyalty to the regime's goals. This environment not only sustains but actively amplifies genocidal ideologies, ensuring their widespread penetration into mainstream Russian society.

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References

- Akhmedova, Y. 2023. Fanaty voiny: Kak futbol'nye khuligany voyuyut v Ukraine i kak s etim svyazany Vladislav Surkov i "Yedinaya Rossiya," Cherta, 13 March, <https://cherta.media/story/fans-of-war/>.
- Akopov, P. 2023. Putin Predupredil ob Ugroze Sushchestvovaniyu Russkogo Naroda, RIA Novosti, 27 February. <https://ria.ru/20230227/putin-1854465327.html>.
- Alperovich, V. 2022. Dve kampanii: Antiimigrantskaya i vtoraya ukrainskaya. Publichnaya aktivnost ultrapravykh grupp, Zima-vesna 2022 goda, Sova, 1 July <https://www.sova-center.ru/racism-xenophobia/publications/2022/7/d46545/>.
- Anderson, C. 2022. 'There Will Be no Mercy' Putin Mouthpiece Warns of 'Concentration Camps, Sterilisation', Express, 5 May, <https://www.express.co.uk/news/world/1605292/putin-news-russia-ukraine-war-concentration-camps-sterilisation-vn>.
- Andriy, K. 2017. Mikhail Kazon Ukrainu raschelnit', a miliony neugodnykh unichtozhit', YouTube, 23 February, <https://youtu.be/vyLkeQxVnfA?si=dQNavgWx50ddGumN>.
- Britskaya, T. and V. Prokushev. 2023. "Budem sudit sami – Kak schitayem nuzhnym," Novaya gazeta, 30 March, <https://novayagazeta.ru/articles/2023/03/30/budem-sudit-sami-kak-schitayem-nuzhnym>.
- Costello, K. 2009. The Conceptualization of Genocide in the International Media: A Case Study of Darfur, Western Kentucky University, <https://digitalcommons.wku.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1076&context=theses>.
- Criado, M. A. 2022. How Nazi Propaganda Dehumanized Jews to Facilitate the Holocaust, El País, 4 December, <https://english.elpais.com/society/2022-12-04/how-nazi-propaganda-dehumanized-jews-to-facilitate-the-holocaust.html>.
- Dalton, B. 2023. A Field Guide to Wagner Group Bloggers: Russia's New Mercenary Media Elite, new America, 14 February, <https://www.newamerica.org/future-frontlines/reports/wagner-group-bloggers-field-guide/>.
- Davis, J. 2022a. Twitter, 24 October, <https://twitter.com/JuliaDavisNews/status/1584365167176871936>.
- Davis, J. 2022b. Twitter, 20 November, <https://twitter.com/JuliaDavisNews/status/1594146245337288705>.
- Davis, J. 2022c. Twitter, 28 November, <https://twitter.com/JuliaDavisNews/status/1597089807171485696?t=4IWKcFRZxp3D97Fzs8meuQ&s=19>.
- Davis, J. 2024. *In Their Own Words. How Russian Propagandists Reveal Putin's Intentions*. Stuttgart: Ibidem New York: Columbia University Press.
- Dryachuk, K. 2024. Rosiyskyi propahandyst Trynadsatyi zaklykav ubyvaty ukrainskykh ditei, Instytut masovoi informatsii, 13 March,

- <https://imi.org.ua/news/rosijskyj-propagandyst-trynadtsyatyj-zaklykav-ubyvaty-ukrayinskyh-ditej-i59913>.
- Dudko, O. 2022. "A Conceptual Limbo of Genocide: Russian Rhetoric, Mass Atrocities in Ukraine, and the Current Definition's Limits." *Canadian Slavonic Papers* 64, no. 2–3: 133–145.
- Fokht, E., S. Goryashko, and O. Ivshina. 2023. "Armiya na polstavki". Kto upravlyayet rossiyskimi neregulyarnymi formirovaniyami, voyuyushchimi v Ukraine?. BBC, 21 November, <https://www.bbc.com/russian/news-67454788>.
- Galleotti, M. 2019. *We Need to Talk About Putin: How the West Gets Him Wrong*. Ebury Press.
- Garner, I. 2023. "'We've Got to Kill Them': Responses to Bucha on Russian Social Media Groups." *Journal of Genocide Research* 25, no. 3–4: 418–425.
- Hoskins, A., and P. Shchelin. 2023. "The War Feed: Digital War in Plain Sight." *American Behavioral Scientist* 67, no. 3: 455–463.
- Human Rights Watch. 2024. "The Massalit Will Not Come Home" Ethnic Cleansing and Crimes Against Humanity in El Geneina, West Darfur, Sudan https://www.hrw.org/sites/default/files/media_2024/05/sudan0524web_0.pdf.
- Ioffe, Y. 2023. "Forcibly Transferring Ukrainian Children to the Russian Federation: A Genocide?" *Journal of Genocide Research* 25, no. 3–4: 315–351.
- Irvin-Erickson, D. 2017. "Genocide Discourses: American and Russian Strategic Narratives of Conflict in Iraq and Ukraine." *Politics and Governance* 5, no. 3: 130–145.
- Kalikh, A. and Y. Dzhibladze. 2023. Incitement to Genocide Against Ukrainians in Russian Propaganda, Centre for Democratic Integrity, <https://democratic-integrity.eu/kalikh-dzhibladze-incitement-to-genocide-against-ukrainians/>.
- Karpovich O. 2022. Na puti k realnoi denatsifikatsii, Izvestiya, 25 October <https://iz.ru/1415500/oleg-karpovich/na-puti-k-realnoi-denatifikatsii>.
- Kolsto, P. 2023. "Ukrainians and Russians as 'One People': An Ideologeme and Its Genesis." *Ethnopolitics (Online First)* 24, no. 2: 139–158. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17449057.2023.2247664>.
- Koltsova, M. 2023. "Nam pridetsya ikh perevospitvat": Mariya Lvova-Belova o detyakh, vyvezennykh iz Ukrainy, Vot Tak, 11 May <https://vot-tak.tv/novosti/11-05-2023-nam-pridetsya-ih-perevospityvat-mariya-lvova-belova-o-detyah-vyvezennykh-iz-ukrainy>.
- Komin, M. 2024. Late-Stage Putinism: The War in Ukraine and Russia's Shifting Ideology, European Council on Foreign Relations, 18 June, <https://ecfr.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Late-stage-Putinism-The-war-in-Ukraine-and-Russias-shifting-ideology.pdf>.
- Korshak, S. 2023. *Pro-Russian Neo-Nazi Shot in the Head at Russian Checkpoint Dies*. Kyiv Post, 9 February, <https://www.kyivpost.com/post/12000>.
- Kotliuk, G. 2023. "Colonization of Minds: Ukraine Between Russian Colonialism and Western Orientalism." *Frontiers in Sociology* 8: 1–8.
- Kovalev, A. 2022. Putin Has a New Opposition—And It's Furious at Defeat in Ukraine. Foreign Policy, 12 September, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2022/09/12/russia-ukraine-war-defeat-opposition-putin-stab-in-the-back-conspiracy-theory-far-right/>.
- Krasovskiy, A. 2022. Mobilizatsiya podkhodit k kontsu, antonimy s Antonom Krasovskim, 18 October <https://antonimy.mave.digital/ep-198>.
- Laruelle, M. 2023. Russia's Ideological Construction in the Context of the War in Ukraine, Institut français des Relations Internationales, 22 March, <https://www.ifri.org/en/studies/russias-ideological-construction-on-context-war-ukraine>.
- Lizan, I. 2023. Poteryav golovu, po volosam ne plachut: o glavnoi utrate Ukrainy, Ukraina.ru, 24 August <https://ukraina.ru/20230824/1048901256.html>.
- LobanIzdat 2023. Pavel Gubarev. Dengi ili mech. Puť k pobede! YouTube, 22 September, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GZHU85s6wfQ>.
- Makarychev, A., and S. Medvedev. 2024. *Biopower in Putin's Russia: From Taking Care to Taking Lives*. Central European University Press.
- Medvedev, S. 2020. *The Return of the Russian Leviathan*. Polity.
- Medvedev, S. 2023. *A War Made in Russia*. Polity.
- Mennecke, O. 2024. "'Kyiv Regime,' 'Junta,' 'Neo-Nazis,' 'Ethnic Jew': Discursive Derogation of Ukrainian Authorities and Enemy-Other Constructions in Vladimir Putin's Speeches." *Canadian Slavonic Papers (Online First)* 66, no. 3–4: 323–347. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00085006.2024.2415798>.
- Minchenia, A., B. Tornquist-Plewa, and Y. Yurchuk. 2018. "Humour as a Mode of Hegemonic Control: Comic Representations of Belarusian and Ukrainian Leaders in Official Russian Media." In *Cultural and Political Imaginaries in Putin's Russia*, edited by N. Bernsand and B. Tornquist-Plewa, 211–231. Leiden and Boston: Brill Academic Publishers.
- Mirskiy, A. 2022. My khotim ubivat: "Meduza" rasskazyvayet, kak (i zachem) neonatsisty iz Rosii otravilis "denatsifitsirovat" Ukrainu, Meduza, 8 July <https://meduza.io/feature/2022/07/08/my-hotim-ubivat>.
- Ndairo, K. 2019. In Rwanda, We Know all About Dehumanizing Language, the Atlantic, 13 April, <https://www.theatlantic.com/ideas/archive/2019/04/rwanda-shows-how-hateful-speech-leads-violence/587041/>.
- Nicolosi, R. 2022. "Paranoia, Resentment, and Reenactment: The Russian Political Discourse on the War in Ukraine." *Ab Imperio* 3: 247–261.
- Nikiforova, V. 2022. Kak vylechit' ukraintsev ot stokgolmskogo sindroma, RIA Novosti, 2 March <https://ria.ru/20220302/ukraina-1775974455.html?in=t>.
- Novic, E. 2016. *The Concept of Cultural Genocide: An International Law Perspective*. Oxford University Press.
- Novye izvestiya 2023. Direktor pravoslavnogo radio "Radonezh" prizval szhigať i rezať glotki ukraintsam, 3 August, <https://newizw.ru/news/2023-08-03/direktor-pravoslavnogo-radio-radonezh-prizval-szhigať-i-rezať-glotki-ukraintsam-415384>.
- Oksamytna, K. 2023. "Imperialism, Supremacy, and the Russian Invasion of Ukraine." *Contemporary Security Policy* 44, no. 4: 497–512.
- Oksamytna, K. 2024. Russia's Status as a Colonial Power. E-International Relations, 1 November, <https://www.e-ir.info/2024/11/01/russias-status-as-a-colonial-power/2024>.
- Ploky, S. and M. Higgins. 2023. Serhii Ploky: Russia Thought It Was Invading the Ukraine of 2014, Chatham House, 22 November <https://www.chathamhouse.org/publications/the-world-today/2023-06/serhi-i-ploky-russia-thought-it-was-invading-ukraine-2014>.
- Poberezhnyi, V. 2024. Why Russia's Memory Policy in Occupied Territories Leaves Some Ukrainian Monuments Standing, Kyiv Independent, 3 October, <https://kyivindependent.com/opinion-why-russias-memory-policy-in-occupied-territories-leaves-some-ukrainian-monuments-standing/>.
- Pomerantsev, P. 2022. Russia's Genocidal Propaganda Must Not Be Passed Off as Freedom of Speech, the Guardian, 16 October, <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2022/oct/16/propaganda-russia-ukraine-war-crimes-accountability>.
- Pynnöniemi, K. 2016. "The Metanarratives of Russian Strategic Deception." In *Fog of Falsehood: Russian Strategy of Deception and*

- the Conflict in Ukraine*, edited by K. Pynnöniemi and A. R.cz, 71–125. Finish Institute of International Relations.
- Pynnöniemi, K., and K. Parppe. 2024. “Understanding Russia’s War Against Ukraine: Political, Eschatological and Cataclysmic Dimensions.” *Journal of Strategic Studies* 47, no. 6–7: 832–859.
- Radio svoboda. 2024a. Egor Guzenko—blogger Trinadtsaty—uyekhal iz SIZO na voynu v Ukraine, 15 November <https://www.svoboda.org/a/egor-guzenko---blogger-trinadtsaty---uehal-iz-sizo-na-voynu-v-ukraine/33203908.html>.
- Radio Svoboda. 2024b. Ezhednevnyye repressii. Kak v Rossii presleduyut za kritiku voyny, 24 February <https://www.svoboda.org/a/ezhednevnyye-repressii-kak-v-rossii-presleduyut-za-kritiku-voyny/32832376.html>.
- Ramakrishna, K. 2020. “Understanding Myanmar’s Buddhist Extremists: Some Preliminary Musings.” *New England Journal of Public Policy* 32, no. 2: 4.
- Riabchuk, M. 2016. “Ukrainians as Russia’s Negative ‘Other’.” *Communist and Post-Communist Studies* 49, no. 1: 75–85.
- Riabchuk, M. 2017. On the “Wrong” and “Right” Ukrainians. Aspen Institute, 14 March. <https://www.aspeninstitute.org/article/2017/on-the-wrong-and-right-ukrainians/>.
- Rondeaux, C., B. Dalton, and J. Deer. 2022. *Wagner Group Contingent Rusich on the Move Again*. New America, 26 January, <https://www.newamerica.org/future-frontlines/blogs/wagner-group-contingent-rusich-on-the-move-again/>.
- Russian Media Monitor. 2023a. Russian Propagandist Challenges Zelensky to a Duel, YouTube, 20 May, https://youtu.be/_PaTFjydwN8?si=edfnhcSihwzv_MKA.
- Russian Media Monitor. 2023b. Senator Wants to Beat the Wrong Ideas Out of Ukrainian Children. YouTube, 22 October, https://youtu.be/jUcRmBJIT_g?si=7lj6enDOssfFfeh.
- Russkiy Styag. 2022. “Razgovor s Russkim Chelovekom, Yevgeniem (pozyvnoi Topaz).” YouTube, 19 April. <https://youtu.be/LV66KzyjoVA>.
- Savage, R. 2007. ““Disease Incarnate”: Biopolitical Discourse and Genocidal Dehumanisation in the Age of Modernity.” *Journal of Historical Sociology* 20, no. 3: 404–440.
- Savage, R. 2009. *Genocidal Dehumanisation as a Discursive Strategy in the Modern Era*. Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Sidney
- Scarr, F. 2023. Twitter, 11 January, https://twitter.com/francis_scarr/status/1613173989311913985.
- Severodonetsk.novyny. 2022. “My vas ubyom. Ubyom million, ubyom pyat millionov, khoť vsekhn istrebim”—Pavel Gubarev. Youtube, 12 October, <https://youtu.be/dC6qGAWJwaI?si=xFolWCqjwLy6E5-I>.
- Shalunov, S. 2022. *Vladimir Putin’s Failing Invasion Is Fueling the Rise of Russia’s Far Right*. Atlantic Council, 14 December, <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/ukrainealert/vladimir-putins-failing-invasion-is-fueling-the-rise-of-russias-far-right/>.
- Skachko, A. 2023. Kak ukraintsam spasti bessmesrtnuyu dushu i brennoye telo, Ukraina.ru, 5 June, <https://ukraina.ru/20230605/1046890379.html>.
- Stent, A. 2019. *Putin’s World: Russia Against the West and with the Rest*. Twelve.
- STV. 2022. “Vy lichno khotite unishtožiť Ukrainu?” Vot chto Na eto otvetil uchastnik SVO, 19 October <https://ctv.by/news/obshchestvo/vy-lichno-hotite-unishtožiť-ukrainu-vot-chto-na-eto-otvetil-uchastnik-svo>.
- Sumlenny, S. 2022. Post on X, 28 August, <https://archive.is/yX5WP>.
- Takševa, T. 2015. “Genocidal Rape, Enforced Impregnation, and the Discourse of Serbian National Identity.” *CLCWeb: Comparative Literature and Culture* 17, no. 3: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.7771/1481-4374.2638>.
- Townsend, E. 2014. “Hate Speech or Genocidal Discourse? An Examination of Anti-Roma Sentiment in Contemporary Europe.” *PORTAL Journal of Multidisciplinary International Studies* 11, no. 1: 3287.
- Tumanov, G. 2015. Poslevoennyye Deistviya, Kommersant, 23 March, <https://www.kommersant.ru/doc/2688561>.
- Ukraina.ru. 2022. Aleksandr “Varyag” Matyushin: Ryadovyye ukrainskie natsionalisty mogut nachat’ gorodskuyu gerilyu, 13 July <https://ukraina.ru/20210809/1032021235.html>.
- Velychenko, S., J. Ruane, and L. Hrynevych, eds. 2022. *Ireland and Ukraine. Essays in Comparative History and Politics*. Stuttgart: Ibidem, and New York: Columbia University Press.
- VGTRK. 2015. Proekt “Ukraina,” Smotrim <https://smotrim.ru/brand/58921>.
- Voroshilov, M. 2023. Gubarev nabrosilsya na Girkina, ustroiv skandal: “on lzhets i lsterik,” Dialog.ua, 26 November https://www.dialog.ua/russia/285443_1700992516.
- Zhurzhenko, T. 2023. Terror, Collaboration, and Resistance: Russian Rule in the Newly Occupied Territories in Ukraine, Eurozine, 17 January, <https://www.eurozine.com/terror-collaboration-and-resistance/>.

Telegram Channels

- Aksyonov, Z 82, 30 March 2022, <https://t.me/Aksenov82/652>.
- Medvedev, Dmitriy. 5 April 2022. https://t.me/medvedev_telegram/34.
- DShRG Rusich. 2 April 2023. <https://dzen.ru/a/ZKcSYkLX4j4IgQCn>.
- DShRG Rusich, 5 August 2023, <https://t.me/dshrg2/1119>.
- DShRG Rusich. 8 August 2024. <https://t.me/dshrg2/2178>.
- Kholmogorov 22 August 2022, <https://t.me/holmogortalks/23593>.
- NeShutki, 15 February 2023, <https://t.me/neshutki1/8995>.
- Obyknovennyi tsarizm, 4 April 2023, <https://t.me/ordinaryczarizm/1544>.
- Syny monarkhii, 8 September 2022, <https://t.me/SonOfMonarchy/7644>.
- Trinadtsaty, Egor Guzenko 2 April 2024, https://t.me/Z13_Separ/27099.
- Trinadtsaty, Egor Guzenko 23 December 2023, https://t.me/Z13_Separ/32593.
- Ugolnyi, Vladislav. 4 August 2022. https://t.me/zola_of_renovation/2485.
- Ugolnyi, Vladislav. 18 July 2023, https://t.me/zola_of_renovation/5530.
- Ugolnyi, Vladislav. 30 November 2023, https://t.me/zola_of_renovation/6472.
- Chicherina, Yulia. 31.12.2022. https://t.me/julia_chicherina/2539.
- Chicherina, Yulia. 1.11.2023. https://t.me/julia_chicherina/2931.
- Zapiski avantyurista [Igor Mangushev]. 2 April, 2022. <https://t.me/BeregTime/4899>.
- Zapiski avantyurista [Igor Mangushev], 25 August 2022, <https://t.me/BeregTime/5963>.